

THE ROLE OF MUSIC CULTURE IN THE AESTHETIC EDUCATION OF
SCHOOLCHILDREN

Ashurova Sadoqat Samatovna

2nd year master's student of Bukhara International University

Annotation: This article analyzes the importance and role of music culture in the aesthetic education of schoolchildren. The article discusses the role of music education in the formation of students' aesthetic worldview, the possibilities of music culture lessons in providing aesthetic education, the influence of national and world musical culture samples on students' worldview, and the development of young people's creative abilities through music. According to the results of the research, ways to more effectively organize aesthetic education in music culture lessons, innovative methods and modern approaches are proposed.

Keywords: *aesthetic education, music culture, school education, national values, creative abilities, personal development, artistic taste, musical thinking, innovative approaches.*

**Maktab o'quvchilarini estetik tarbiyalashda
musiqa madaniyati fanining o'rni**

Ashurova Sadoqat Samatovna – Buxoro Xalqaro
universiteti 2 – kurs magistranti

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola maktab o'quvchilarining estetik tarbiyasida musiqa madaniyati fanining ahamiyati va rolini tahlil etadi. Maqolada musiqa ta'limining o'quvchilar estetik dunyoqarashini shakllantirishdagi o'rni, musiqa madaniyati darslarining estetik tarbiya berishdagi imkoniyatlari, milliy va jahon musiqa madaniyati namunalarining o'quvchilar dunyoqarashiga ta'siri, hamda musiqa orqali yoshlarning ijodiy qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirish masalalari yoritib berilgan. Tadqiqot natijalariga ko'ra, musiqa madaniyati darslarida estetik tarbiyani yanada samarali tashkil etish yo'llari, innovatsion usullar va zamonaviy yondashuvlar taklif etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: *estetik tarbiya, musiqa madaniyati, maktab ta'limi, milliy qadriyatlar, ijodiy qobiliyatlar, shaxs kamoloti, badiiy did, musiqa tafakkuri, innovatsion yondashuvlar.*

In modern society, the issue of educating the younger generation in a comprehensive manner is one of the most urgent tasks. Aesthetic education plays a particularly important role in the spiritual and moral development of a person. Aesthetic education is a pedagogical process aimed at developing a person's abilities to feel, understand and create beauty, which serves to increase the overall cultural level of the individual.

Various disciplines contribute to the formation of aesthetic education of students in the school education system. However, the science of musical culture, with its effective tools and wide possibilities, is of particular importance in this process. Music has the power to directly affect human emotions, spiritually enrich a person, expand his worldview and enrich his spiritual world. It is through the art of music that children form and develop a sense of elegance, beauty, and artistic taste. This article discusses the role and importance of the subject of musical culture in the aesthetic education of schoolchildren, the current state of musical education, ways to improve it, and innovative approaches.

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Aesthetic education is a pedagogical process aimed at educating a person in the spirit of understanding, appreciating, and applying beauty to life. Through this process, students develop artistic taste, a sense of beauty, a sense of elegance, and creative abilities. The main goals of aesthetic education are as follows:

1. To form the ability to feel and understand beauty in students;
2. To master national and universal artistic and aesthetic values;
3. To develop creative abilities;
4. To form artistic taste;
5. To educate aesthetic ideals.

The subject of musical culture serves as one of the most effective tools in implementing the above goals. Music affects students' emotions, awakens a sense of beauty in them, develops creative thinking, and helps them understand national and universal values.

The subject of musical culture is an integral part of the school curriculum. It not only expands students' knowledge of musical art, but also increases their general cultural level, enriches their worldview and plays an important role in achieving spiritual maturity.

Musical culture in schools is carried out in the following areas:

1. Musical literacy - familiarization with musical notation, the basics of music theory, musical terms;
2. Listening to music - listening and analyzing samples of national and world musical culture;
3. Singing in a group - developing voice tuning, ensemble feeling through singing in a choir;
4. Musical creativity - creating simple melodies, improvisation, rhythmic movements.

All this serves to form students' aesthetic worldview, feel and understand beauty, and develop artistic taste.

Music culture lessons affect the aesthetic education of students in the following areas:

Music is a type of art that directly affects the emotional world of a person. In the process of listening to and performing musical works, students experience various emotions, their emotional world is enriched, and their feelings are refined. This helps to form not only their musical, but also their general aesthetic outlook.

In music culture lessons, students get acquainted with musical works of various genres, styles, and periods. In this process, they develop the ability to select artistically valuable works, distinguish beauty from ordinary and superficial things. As a result, their artistic taste is formed and improved.

Music lessons are of great importance in developing students' creative abilities. Creative activities such as creating melodies, improvising, and coming up with movements to music expand students' imagination and develop creative thinking.

In music culture lessons, students get acquainted with our national musical heritage and masterpieces of world musical culture. In this process, they study Uzbek folk music, maqom art, compositional work, as well as samples of world classical music. This instills in students a sense of national pride and respect for universal human values.

Uzbek folk musical culture is very rich and diverse. Introducing schoolchildren to samples of our national musical heritage, instilling in them feelings of love and respect for national musical art is one of the important areas of aesthetic education.

The study of national musical heritage is carried out in the following areas:

1. Folk songs and lapars - labor, ritual, lyrical songs, children's folklore;
2. Samples of instrumental music - melodies, paths, melodies;
3. Maqom art – Shashmaqom, Khorezm maqoms, Fergana-Tashkent maqom paths;

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4. Compositional creativity – Muhammadjon Umarjonov, Yunus Rajabiy, Fakhridin Sodiqov and others.

In the process of studying national music samples, students absorb the spiritual heritage of our people, understand our national values, develop a sense of national pride and honor. This has a positive effect on their aesthetic education.

In music culture lessons, along with studying our national musical heritage, it is important to get acquainted with the masterpieces of world music culture. This broadens the students' worldview, teaches them to respect the cultures of different peoples, and helps them understand universal values.

The study of world music culture is carried out in the following areas:

1. Classical music samples – I.S. Bach, V.A. Mozart, L.V. Beethoven and others;
2. Musical creativity of different nations – musical culture of Russian, German, French, Italian and other nations;
3. Modern music trends – jazz, pop, rock and other genres.

By studying the masterpieces of world musical culture, students understand the unique features of the cultures of different peoples, learn to appreciate them. This enriches their aesthetic outlook, develops the ability to feel and perceive beauty.

To increase the effectiveness of musical culture lessons in providing aesthetic education, it is advisable to work in the following areas:

The use of modern pedagogical technologies, interactive methods, multimedia tools in musical culture lessons increases students' interest in the subject, increases their activity. For example:

- Using audio and video materials in the process of listening to music;
- Using interactive methods for analyzing musical works;
- Using modern technologies for creating and performing music.

Connecting musical culture lessons with other subjects systematizes students' knowledge and broadens their worldview. For example:

- The connection between literature and music (poems and songs, epics and opera);
- History and music (musical culture of different eras);
- Mathematics and music (rhythm, meter, note lengths);
- Art and music (connecting musical works with works of fine art).

In music culture lessons, along with theoretical knowledge, great attention should be paid to practical activities. Students gain a deeper understanding of the essence of musical art through practical activities such as singing, playing musical instruments, performing rhythmic movements, and creating simple melodies.

Organizing various music-related clubs (choir, ensemble, orchestra) at school and involving students in them creates a great opportunity to improve their musical culture, develop their creative abilities, and form their aesthetic education.

Holding various musical events (concerts, competitions, festivals, creative meetings) at school increases students' interest in musical art and creates an opportunity to demonstrate their creative abilities.

The effectiveness of music culture lessons in providing aesthetic education largely depends on the professional skills of the teacher. A music teacher must have the following qualities:

1. High professional training - deep knowledge in the field of music theory and history, music pedagogy and psychology;
2. Performance skills - singing, playing musical instruments, conducting skills;

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3. Pedagogical skills - the ability to organize a lesson in an interesting way, activate students, develop their abilities;
4. Creative approach - the ability to creatively approach the teaching process, use innovative methods;
5. Personal culture - the teacher himself must be a person of high culture, demonstrate his own aesthetic taste.

A music teacher must be an example for students during the lesson, be able to interest them in musical art, and work taking into account the individual abilities of each student.

The following modern approaches to teaching music culture give effective results:

Education taking into account the individual characteristics, abilities and interests of each student. This approach helps students to fully realize their potential.

To form in students not only knowledge and skills, but also the ability to apply them in life. It is important that students can apply the knowledge they have gained in music culture lessons in everyday life, independently analyze musical works, and express their own tastes.

The use of modern information and communication technologies makes music culture lessons more interesting and effective. Virtual concert halls, music creation programs, and online music resources greatly assist students in learning the art of music.

Providing students with the opportunity to work on various projects develops their creative abilities and teaches them to think independently. For example, projects such as "My Favorite Composer", "Journey through the History of Music", "Music and Nature".

Integrating the study of musical culture with other subjects systematizes students' knowledge and broadens their worldview.

The subject of musical culture occupies an important place in the aesthetic education of schoolchildren. Musical art affects the feelings of students, awakens in them a sense of beauty, forms artistic taste, develops creative abilities and helps to achieve spiritual maturity.

To increase the effectiveness of musical culture lessons in providing aesthetic education, it is important to introduce innovative methods, ensure interdisciplinary connections, increase attention to practical activities, organize club work, and hold musical events.

The professional skills of a music teacher, his individual approach to students, and the use of modern pedagogical technologies serve to increase the effectiveness of musical culture lessons in providing aesthetic education.

In conclusion, through the study of musical culture, schoolchildren develop the ability to feel and understand beauty, artistic taste, and creative thinking. They assimilate national and universal values, and as a result, a highly spiritual and well-rounded individual is formed.

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